

CONTENT OF FORMING THE GENERAL CULTURAL COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS BASED ON A SYNERGETIC APPROACH

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Abstract. *In the article, it is claimed that the methodological principles, pedagogical, psychological, spiritual, moral, communicative characteristics of the formation of general cultural competence of elementary school students based on a synergistic approach, the characteristics of general cultural competence, and the systematic organization of pedagogical activities in its content are necessary. Evaluation of the conditions, implementation based on the conditions and principles of the successful formation of the desired type of general competence, opinions on the implementation of the process of forming the general cultural competence of elementary school students based on the synergetic approach are described.*

Keywords: *synergetic approach, universal competence, education, cooperation, moral, cognitive, emotional, innovative thinking, national and universal values, patriotism.*

INTRODUCTION

As the independence of our country becomes increasingly stable on the global scale every year, its future depends on the development of today's generation into knowledgeable and spiritually mature individuals. In this context, it is crucial to improve the effectiveness of shaping a well-rounded, active, and developed personality for the human psyche, and the role of psychological-pedagogical science and its correct application in practice is essential. As Uzbekistan continues to strengthen its independence globally, its future depends on the development of today's generation into knowledgeable, spiritually mature individuals. In this regard, increasing the effectiveness of shaping a full, active, and well-rounded personality for the human psyche is of utmost importance in psychological and pedagogical science and its application in practice. A state that thinks about its bright and prosperous future will certainly pay serious attention to the education of a well-rounded generation and will take all necessary measures in this noble path.

The decree of the President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of May 11, 2022, "On approving the national program for the development of public education for 2022-2026"[1] PD-134, the decree of January 28, 2022, "On the strategy of development of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" [2]PD-60, the resolution of November 6, 2020, "On additional measures for further improving the education system" PR-4884[3], the decree of March 26, 2021, "On measures for the radical improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work" PR-5040[4], and the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the "Psychological and pedagogical support for students" 577[5], and the development of the Regulation on the organization of psychological services in general education and secondary-specialized state educational institutions - all

contribute to the implementation of the tasks set out in other regulatory and legal documents related to this area. This research plays a significant role in the implementation of the tasks defined in these documents.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The synergetic approach is being studied and applied in practice by scholars as a new direction in today's modern education system. The concept of synergetics has been interpreted differently in various dictionaries. In particular, in the book "Explanatory Dictionary of Pedagogy" by J. Khasanboyev and others, synergetics is described as a system that initially aims to identify general principles that operate equally in both all things and events and in the parts that make them up, based on the theory of complexes.[9]

Scholar G.M. Kojaspirova defines the concept of "synergetics" as being closely related to the concept of "education" (translated from Greek, it means "acting together" or "cooperation"). [13]

Scholar V.A. Ignatova identifies three key components of applying the ideas of synergetics in education:

- the didactic aspects of adapting the ideas of synergetics to the content of education;
- using them in modeling and forecasting the development of the education system;
- applying them in the management of the educational process[10].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The article outlines the methodological foundations for forming the general cultural competence of primary school students based on a synergetic approach, theoretical descriptions of their pedagogical and psychological characteristics, and the unique qualities of general cultural competence. It also addresses the necessary conditions for organizing pedagogical activities to develop it. The process of forming the general cultural competence of primary school students based on a synergetic approach is discussed, with reflections on its practical application. The article includes an analysis of scientific works by both foreign and local researchers and presents suggestions and recommendations for the application of a synergetic approach in developing the general cultural competence of primary school students.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The education system must respond to the changing demands of the times, and today, the importance of the synergetic approach in organizing the pedagogical process effectively is increasing. Synergetics analyzes the changes and interactions of various systems by studying their mutual influences and development processes. The application of the synergetic approach in education helps in forming students' general cultural competence and teaching them knowledge, skills, and competencies in an integrated manner. The synergetic approach is considered from the perspective of the subject of the learning process. In this approach, the teacher and the student are equal subjects of the pedagogical process, and a pedagogy of collaboration and self-organization is developed. The synergetic approach ensures high results by applying the principle of humanism, which is a component of general cultural competence, through the development of the student's educational and motivational processes. Understanding the world through synergetics plays an important role in education: synergetic thinking is characterized by openness, dialogism, and communication. Synergetics encourages parents, as subjects of the virtual-pedagogical process, to explore the most complex internal laws of human life. Synergetic education, like new pedagogy, is about self-education, where people determine their own fate by motivating their abilities. The

synergetic approach allows us to view each subject of the pedagogical process (parent, student, teacher) as a self-developing small system that transitions from development to self-development. Therefore, shaping the pedagogical culture of parents should be one of the most important tasks of modern society and a part of state social policy.

Based on his own experience, the American pedagogical psychologist David Kolb, famous for his theory of experiential learning, emphasizes the importance of experience and reflection (the significance of self-analysis) in the formation of general cultural competence [15].

Researcher G. Mustafayeva, in her scientific work, presents the idea that teaching youth through moral values and general cultural competence in the education system is an effective method [7].

According to M.S. Nazarova, “National and general cultural competence means being loyal to one’s homeland, compassionate toward others, believing in universal and national values, understanding works of art, dressing neatly, adhering to cultural norms, and leading a healthy lifestyle.[12]”

In our opinion, general cultural competence is an educational process aimed at developing a number of human qualities, such as loyalty to one’s homeland, honoring national traditions and values, protecting the environment, having a love for books, respecting elders, and showing kindness to the young.

Famous pedagogue A.S. Makarenko argued that proper upbringing should begin as early as possible, as re-education later on is much harder and requires more effort and knowledge. He stated, “It is easier to educate a child properly and normally than to re-educate them.” Makarenko specifically highlights the importance of respect and greeting adults, which is one of the components of general cultural competence.

From the ideas presented above, it can be understood that the process of shaping the general cultural competence of primary school students during "Upbringing" classes largely depends on the methods and tools used in the lesson, as well as how interesting and meaningful the lessons are through modern approaches.

We have developed a set of practical tasks for "Upbringing" lessons aimed at shaping the general cultural competence of primary school students based on the synergetic approach. The exercises in the set are designed for the components of general cultural competence and are created using the synergetic approach. These exercises include tasks like “Do it with your parents’ help”, “Find out from your teacher,” and “Do it with your friend.” The difficulty level of the tasks is structured based on the age characteristics of primary school students, following the principle from easy to difficult.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the formation of primary school students' general cultural competence based on a synergetic approach in the educational process contributes to raising the effectiveness of education to a new level and creates the foundation for the development of a general cultural worldview in students. Based on this approach, during the educational process in primary school, through teacher-student collaboration, the components of general cultural competence are formed, while simultaneously conducting analytical analysis. The cooperation between parents and students in the theoretical and practical process ensures the harmony of their activities, ultimately leading to the upbringing of a well-rounded, mature, independent, and, most importantly, culturally competent generation.

BU QIZIQ!

Buyuk Xitoy devori- dunyoning qadimiy yodgorliklaridan biri. Xitoy bo'ylab 8000 kilometrgacha cho'zilgan bo'lib, uning qurilishi davomida yuz minglab quruvchilar 10 yildan ko'proq mehnat qilishgan.

2- topshiriq. Siz bilgan millatlar nomini yozing.

1.
2.
3.
4.
5.

3- topshiriq. Vatanimiz O'zbekiston Respublikasi haqida 5 ta ma'lumot yozing.

4- topshiriq. O'tmishdagi vatanparvar insonlardan kimlarni bilasiz?

Maqol. Vatanning tinch- sen tinch.

5- topshiriq. Vatan haqida 2 ta she'r yod oling.

Bajardim ☒	Bajara olmadim. ☐
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Picture 1. Examples from the set of tasks.

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